

Malaria Vaccine for Disease Control in Nigeria: An Overview

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Abstract

Background: Malaria morbidity and mortality have decreased considerably over the previous two decades worldwide. Nonetheless, in certain areas where these precautions have been applied, malaria sickness and death rates remain high. As a result, additional and supplementary approaches are needed to lower the disease burden and ultimately accomplish the goal of a malaria-free world. In 2023, Nigeria approved the R21 malaria vaccine. This study examines the epidemiology and illness burden of malaria, as well as the technical elements of the malaria vaccine and its implementation in Nigeria.

Methods: This overview was based on papers and research briefs from WHO, UNICEF, and the CDC. This work also involved conducting literature searches on peer-reviewed articles published in databases such as Google Scholar.

Results and conclusion: The R21 vaccine is still in its early phases of deployment, and one major worry is the global health community's cost and finance concerns for expanded rollout, as well as countries' decisions on whether to include the vaccine in national malaria control efforts.

Keywords: Malaria, Immunization, Vaccine, R21 vaccine, Nigeria

Introduction

Malaria has been a major public health concern since its discovery few years ago. Malaria has had a negative impact on families and communities in Sub-Saharan Africa, and it is still the top cause of sickness and death, despite being preventable and treatable (1). One of the reasons is that poor people, particularly those living in rural areas, have limited access to high-quality antimalarial services (1–2). Because of the condition and the costs of therapy, families are locked in a vicious cycle of illness, pain, and poverty (3).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than half of the world's population, primarily in Sub-Saharan Africa, is at risk of contracting malaria and having financial difficulties (1). According to data, over half of the global population was at risk of malaria in 2021. Nonetheless, some populations are regarded to be the most vulnerable to malaria and severe illness (1–4). These include infants, children under the age of five,

pregnant women, and people suffering from Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (1). Furthermore, people with inadequate immunity may relocate to areas with high malaria transmission, such as migrant workers, mobile populations, and travelers (5).

Evidence suggests that malaria morbidity and mortality have decreased considerably during the last two decades (5). Sub-Saharan African countries have made significant progress in the fight against malaria by implementing key WHO-recommended tools such as insecticide-treated mosquito nets, indoor pesticide spraying, and antimalarial medications (2). Nonetheless, in certain areas where these precautions have been applied, malaria sickness and death rates remain high. As a result, new and supplementary interventions are required to further lower the disease burden and ultimately attain the goal of a malaria-free world (3).

In view of these, the Global Technical Strategy (GTS) for Malaria 2016-2030 seeks to reduce global malaria incidence and mortality rates by at least 90% by 2030 (4-6). In 2017, WHO launched Elimination-2020, a dedicated campaign to accelerate malaria elimination. Twenty-five countries took part in this program, which aimed to reduce malaria cases to zero by 2025 (5). Insecticides for vector control and pharmaceuticals for treatment and prevention are at the center of malaria control strategies, but both are vulnerable to biological resistance (1).

While many efforts have been undertaken to improve malaria management and elimination strategies, the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication has highlighted the vital role that malaria vaccinations can play in achieving eradication (7,8). Vaccination is essential to enhance current malaria therapy, diagnostic, and vector control strategies (9). The COVID-19 pandemic increased awareness of the necessity of vaccines in overall disease control and prevention, as well as epidemic preparedness for infectious illnesses. In response to global antimicrobial resistance developments, vaccines have been recognized for their unique role in combating antimicrobial resistance by avoiding illnesses and reducing dependency on antimicrobials (8, 9).

The purpose of this article is to 1) discuss malaria epidemiology and illness load, 2) examine the technical aspects of malaria vaccines, and 3) discuss Nigeria's vaccine rollout.

Methods:

This review was based on publications and research briefs from the World Health Organization, United Nations Children's Fund, and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. This work also included literature searches on peer-reviewed articles from databases such as Google Scholar.

The initial papers on population-based studies of adults, children, and pregnant women that reported malaria morbidity, mortality, incidence, and prevalence. Studies addressing the technical aspects and efficacy of malaria vaccinations were considered. However, studies that contained self-reports of malaria and malaria vaccine were eliminated.

Epidemiology and Disease Burden of Malaria

Global malaria incidence and mortality are expected to be 59 cases per 1,000 people at risk and 15 deaths per 100,000 people at risk in 2019, respectively, showing insufficient progress toward the GTS targets of 35

cases per 1,000 and 7.2 deaths per 100,000 (6). Thus, the WHO strategic advisory group on malaria eradication declared in 2019 that eradicating malaria by 2050 will be difficult, even if present measures are completely ramped up (6-7).

Meanwhile, Nigeria had 68 million malaria cases in 2021, representing 27% of the global burden and 28% of the burden in the WHO African Region (10, 11). The WHO also predicts that severe malaria would kill 194,000 people by 2021, with children under the age of five accounting for over 80% of these deaths. This accounts for 31% of malaria deaths worldwide and 40% in the WHO African Region (10, 11).

Despite the severe burden and difficulty of the COVID-19 pandemic, malaria prevalence has dropped by 26% since 2020, from 413 per 1000 persons to 306 per 1000 in 2021. Prior to the epidemic, the malaria rate was 302 per 1000 people (3,10). During the same time period, the malaria mortality rate fell by 55%, from 2.1 per 1000 individuals in 2020 to 0.9 per 1000 in 2021. The malaria mortality rate in 2019 was 1.2 per 1000 individuals (2,3,10). According to household survey data, malaria prevalence in children assessed by microscopy and rapid diagnostic test (RDT) has reduced from 27% and 45% in 2015 to 22% and 40% in 2021, respectively. Between 2010, the year after the first global campaign began, and 2021, an estimated 166 million malaria cases and 0.85 million malaria deaths were likely prevented (10, 12).

In the meanwhile, most Nigerian states have implemented significant malaria control measures. The Nigerian government and its partners, working via the National Malaria Elimination Program, have made considerable strides in expanding preventive and curative treatments (11). Between 2009 and 2021, more than 220 million insecticide-treated nets were distributed throughout 37 states. The proportion of the population sleeping under insecticide-treated nets the night before the survey increased from 22.9% in 2010 to 36.4% in 2021 (11). The percentage of children under five who slept under an insecticide-treated net the night before the survey increased from 28.9% in 2010 to 41.2% in 2021. The coverage for intermittent malaria preventive medication in pregnancy (two or more doses of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine) rose from 22% in 2015 to 26% in 2020, but declined to 23% in 2021 (11).

Nigeria has greatly expanded seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) for children under the age of five. In 2013, around 209,000 youngsters received SMC in one state. By 2021, the number of

children has risen to more over 24 million across 18 states. In 2021, more than 63% of children who reported having a fever in the two weeks before the household survey sought medical attention. The private formal sector provided care to the majority of children (31%), followed by the informal sector (25%), with the private sector accounting for 45%. The proportion of patients seeking fever treatment has climbed from 6.5% in 2010 to 39% in 2021 (11).

Malaria Vaccine Technical Properties (efficacy, presentation profile, effectiveness)

Malaria vaccines are the most recent therapies for malaria prevention and control. Since the publication of the first malaria vaccine preferred product characteristic in 2014, significant advances in malaria vaccine research and development have happened (2,10). The European Medicines Agency provided the first positive scientific opinion on RTS,S, the malaria vaccine (12-15). The immunization was given the title RTS,S since it was made by combining qualities from the rehash ('R') and T-cell epitope ('T') of the pre-erythrocytic circumsporozoite protein (CSP) of the *Plasmodium falciparum* intestinal sickness parasite with a surface antigen ('S') of the hepatitis B infection and at that point blended with extra hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) to progress decontamination, thus the additional "S" (16-17).

The Malaria RTS,S vaccine is designed to engage the immune system against the liver stage of infection, during which the parasite grows before attacking red blood cells (18-20). According to the mathematical models, implementing the vaccine at high coverage in moderate to high endemicity settings would avoid 10-28% of all malaria deaths in children under the age of five, as well as 200-700 deaths per 100,000 vaccine recipients on a four-dose schedule (15).

In October 2021, the WHO recommended its usage in moderate-to-high transmission scenarios (13-15). Evidence suggests that RTS, S, and other vaccines with intermediate efficacy against clinical malaria have the potential to make a large public health impact if widely adopted (15). The first two years of the malaria vaccine implementation program indicated that the vaccine could be successfully administered.

The malaria vaccine implementation program was created to address outstanding difficulties about the vaccine's public health use. Ghana, Kenya, and Malawi's Ministries of Health have incorporated the RTS,S vaccine into their expanded immunization programs, following standard procedures for new vaccine introductions. Positive uptake in all three countries has exceeded or surpassed expectations for a

new vaccine with a novel schedule. The malaria vaccine pilot test satisfied rigorous procedural standards. The statistical analysis strategy was used to finish the analysis (15).

Since the last meeting of the strategic advisory group of experts on immunization/malaria policy advisory group in 2015 (12-14), further information on safety has become available from sources other than the malaria vaccine implementation program. These extra data include the following: 1) Long-term follow-up of a subset (>3000 children) of phase 3 trial participants for three years after the main study's conclusion; 2) A seasonal use study in more than 6000 children evaluating the individual and combined impact of RTS,S and seasonal malaria chemoprevention; and 3) A trial in approximately 1200 children of various fractional dose regimens of RTS,S (15).

Available safety data from the malaria vaccine implementation program, a large, structured pilot introduction that provided more than 1.7 million RTS,S vaccine doses, and from these additional sources, the working group agrees with the malaria vaccine implementation program data and safety monitoring board that there is no evidence of a causal relationship between the RTS,S vaccine and the three potential safety signals - cerebral malaria, meningitis, or Furthermore, the RTS,S malaria vaccine has been investigated and shown to be safe in HIV-positive and malnourished children (15).

Nonetheless, in weighing benefits and dangers, it was discovered that RTS,S had been shown to protect against clinical and severe malaria, with unknown benefits against malaria-related or all-cause mortality, which the phase 3 trial did not intend to investigate (21). The hazards noted were febrile convulsions after immunization. Furthermore, a significant risk difference for meningitis was observed after vaccination, but the causal relationship remained unknown, with no clear causality model - the excess of meningitis cases in vaccinated children was seen only in the older age group (5-17 months at first vaccination), not the younger age group (15,21).

However, there was no temporal relationship with vaccination, with cases occurring more than 1000 days after the first vaccine dose; meningitis cases clustered by site, with 64% of cases coming from only two of the 11 sites; and etiology was inconsistent, with bacterial, mycobacterial, viral, and no pathogen isolated. Furthermore, it was unclear whether the trial's higher mortality rate among vaccinated girls or the imbalance of cerebral malaria cases (in the context of reduced severe

malaria, of which cerebral malaria is a subcategory) were due to vaccination or more likely chance events. The pooled safety analysis of phase 2 trials revealed no safety signs (21,22).

Overall, it was believed that the vaccine's advantages surpassed its risks when given to children aged 5 to 17 months in a four-dose regimen. However, in children who only received three doses, severe malaria decreased momentarily before increasing again 18 months later. The question of whether it was operationally possible to reach children with high coverage using a 4-dose schedule with the fourth dose given around the age of two, as well as the extent to which the protection seen in children aged 5 to 17 months could be replicated in routine health systems, remained unanswered (15,21).

In January 2016, WHO advised that the 4-dose schedule be utilized in carefully tested pilot implementations with sufficiently large populations of children aged 5 to 17 months in 3-5 different epidemiological contexts in Sub-Saharan Africa with moderate to high transmission (15, 21). Furthermore, it was proposed that the pilot implementations be carried out in stages, with ongoing high coverage of other effective malaria control measures such as long-lasting insecticide-treated nets, access to high-quality diagnosis and treatment, and seasonal malaria chemoprevention as needed (15,21). The international body then approved a phased implementation of the malaria vaccine in 2019 (23).

RTS,S was discovered to be immunogenic and to have moderate protective efficacy against clinical malaria (39%), severe malaria (31.5%), and malaria-related hospitalizations (37.2%) after the initial three-monthly doses, according to evidence from the phase 3 trial results over four years of follow-up in children aged 5 to 17 months at the time of the first vaccination who received a fourth dose 18 months after the primary series (21,24). At six months after the fourth dosage, vaccine efficacy was 42.9%, demonstrating that, while the fourth dose extended the time of protective efficacy, it did not restore it to the level found after the first immunization series. This was most likely attributable to the comparison group's incomplete immunity to natural infection by this point, which could have influenced the difference (15).

However, preliminary data from the first two years of routine vaccination show that the malaria vaccine reduces deadly severe malaria while being safe and easy to administer. This is attributed to a significant decrease in the number of children hospitalized and a decrease in child mortality in the vaccine's age range since its introduction (23). The pilots will continue in the three pilot nations until 2023 to assess the long-

term effects on child mortality and the impact of the fourth vaccine dose. As a result, there is enough evidence of vaccine safety and efficacy to warrant a broad recommendation for its use (25).

The World Health Organization stated in October 2023 that a second malaria vaccine, R21/Matrix-M, will be added to its recommended vaccine for children at risk of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria (26-28). The R21 vaccine contains a high dose of malaria antigen and uses the Matrix-M adjuvant to boost immune response, whereas the RTS,S uses the AS01 adjuvant system to stimulate an immune response (18-20).

Given the similarities between R21 and RTS,S, data and lessons learned from the RTS,S experience, including pilot introductions, guided WHO's evaluation of R21 (29). Furthermore, assessments of public health effects and cost-effectiveness affected WHO's recommendation for R21 (19). Clinical testing of R21 began in 2015, with a first-in-human trial in the United Kingdom. The first R21 experiment in a malaria-endemic region, which included adults aged 18 to 45 from Burkina Faso, was completed in 2017. A phase 2b trial in Nanoro, Burkina Faso, showed proof-of-concept in young children in a region with high seasonal malaria transmission (26-29).

Vaccine efficacy against all clinical malaria episodes in seasonal settings was 75% after the third dose, with a 12-month follow-up. In sites that adopted age-based administration, vaccine efficacy was 67% 12 months after the third dose (26-29). Efficacy ranged from 57% (age-based) to 82% (seasonal). Efficacy against all bouts of clinical malaria was again assessed 20 months later, 6 months after the fourth dose was provided, and available data show that efficacy was maintained (26-29).

Nigeria Vaccine Rollout

On April 17, 2023, Nigeria authorized the R21 malaria vaccine (30, 31). According to (19-20), GAVI determined that the R21 vaccination was the best fit for Nigeria based on the country's requirements and plans, as detailed in its proposal to GAVI. The R21/Matrix-M supplied to Nigeria is a novel malaria vaccine that acts similarly to the RTS,S vaccine (20). However, it is intended to provide better immunity to the malaria parasite while lowering reactions to an unrelated component of the vaccine (19-20). The R21 vaccination is recommended for infants ages 5 to 17 months.

In its early trials, up to 80% of children immunized with the R21 malaria vaccine did not acquire malaria (31-32). The R21 vaccine, which works by creating large quantities of malaria-specific antibodies that aid in malaria defense, has been shown to be safer and more effective than the RTS,S vaccine in preliminary results from a two-year study. In early trials conducted in 2019 and 2020, children aged 5 to 17 months were given three doses before malaria season and a booster 12 months later. During the two-year experiment, up to 80% of children who got the vaccination did not develop clinical malaria (30).

On October 17, 2024, the Nigerian government received 846,200 doses of the R21/Matrix-M malaria vaccine from GAVI, the Vaccine Alliance. Because of the limited supply of doses, the vaccine will only be distributed in two states (18,20). The malaria vaccine, which requires four doses, will be administered to children under the age of one as part of Nigeria's standard immunization program. The initial phase of the implementation will begin in Kebbi and Bayelsa States in November 2024, where malaria is very prevalent, with over 800,000 doses to be distributed (20).

Conclusion

Malaria remains the leading cause of childhood morbidity and mortality in Nigeria. The most susceptible population to the disease lives in rural areas with inadequate access to medical care and treatment. As a result, several stakeholders are concerned about whether particular populations will be able to obtain the vaccine once it is available. This is due to Nigeria's absence of a healthcare system that makes it easy for residents in rural areas to access medical care. Although the R21 vaccine is still in its early stages of deployment, a major concern is the cost and financial decisions made by the global health community for a larger rollout.

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